

Diuretic Activity Evaluation and Phytochemical Screening of Methanolic Extract of *Amorphophallus Commutatus* Leaves, In Wister Rat Models

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ABSTRACT

Amorphophallus commutatus (Araceae) is often found in of Western Ghats, India. *Amorphophallus commutatus* has a number of chemical components that might be used as medicinal agents, the current study aims to investigate the diuretic activity of the methanolic extract of the leaves of *Amorphophallus commutatus* in rats. Soxhlet extraction was used to extract methanol from dried course powdered leaves. Male Wistar rats were given three different oral doses of the extract (100 mg/kg, 200 mg/kg, and 400 mg/kg) along with a control (normal saline, 1ml/kg) and a reference drug (furosemide, 10 mg/kg). To determine the extract's diuretic activity, measurements were made of body weight, urine volume, diuretic action and activity, urine pH, and specific gravity. Urine output was measured at 12 and 24 hours, along with measurements of body weight, urinary pH, electrolyte concentrations, and specific gravity, during the acute study (1 day) and after 7 days in the sub-acute study. The levels of creatinine, urea, and electrolytes in urine and plasma samples were also measured. A one-way ANOVA was used to assess the results. At 400 mg/kg, the extract had significant diuretic effects in comparison to the control and reference drug, according to the findings of a dose-dependent comparison of the extract with the control and reference drug. Additionally, the excretion of Na⁺, K⁺, and Cl⁻ in the urine increased significantly at all doses. Through biochemical research, the extract's diuretic efficacy was further confirmed. These results highlight the need to preserve traditional knowledge and encourage the herb's traditional usage as a diuretic. Taking everything into consideration, the information presented here suggested that *Amorphophallus commutatus* leaves methanolic extract is a good way to produce a diuresis effect.

Keywords: *Amorphophallus commutatus*, traditional medicine, methanolic extract, diuretic activity, Soxhlet extraction, Wistar rats, electrolyte excretion.

INTRODUCTION

Diuretics are pharmacological agents that act on the kidneys to improve the excretion of sodium (Na⁺) and water in urine. These compounds facilitate the removal of excess body water, electrolytes, metabolic waste products, and toxins while helping to maintain fluid and electrolytes balance. Beyond their primary effect on sodium excretion, diuretics influence renal handling of other cations (potassium [K⁺], hydrogen [H⁺], calcium [Ca²⁺], and magnesium [Mg²⁺]) and

anions (chloride [Cl⁻], bicarbonate [HCO₃⁻], and phosphate [H₂PO₄⁻], as well as uric acid metabolism¹. They work by either directly affecting nephron cells or indirectly altering the composition of the filtrate. Diuretics are crucial in the clinical treatment of edema brought on by a number of illnesses, such as hypertension, heart failure, liver cirrhosis, renal disorders, and pulmonary or systemic edema.². Their therapeutic effects result from inhibiting Na⁺ and Cl⁻ reabsorption in the nephron, with subsequent water loss occurring secondary to increased NaCl excretion

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(natriuresis)³. According to their mechanisms of action, these diuretics are often divided into four different classes: potassium-sparing diuretics, carbonic anhydrase inhibitors, loop diuretics, and thiazide diuretics. However, the use of these pharmacological medicines is associated with possible side effects, which highlights the growing interest in investigating natural alternatives⁴. Herbal medicine and their derivatives are currently very significant within modern medical practices. Numerous therapeutic plants and their secondary metabolites have been identified as promising therapeutic agents for the management of renal problems associated with hypertension, providing fresh insights into this pathology's treatment⁵

Amorphophallus commutatus var. *wayanadensis*, a member of the Araceae family, is highlighted in this context. It is a tuberous plant that is widely spread in tropical and subtropical climates and has a high nutritional value and health advantages¹. Many types of *Amorphophallus* have been grown and utilized as medicine and fodder. The medicinal plant *Amorphophallus commutatus* is native to India and has a red listed, making it vulnerable worldwide. Ethnobotanical investigations have shown the traditional use of *A. commutatus* corms for a variety of ailments, including piles, scabies, snake bites, and oral disorders. The mountainous areas of the Western Ghats in India are home to the newly discovered *Amorphophallus* species *A. commutatus* var. *wayanadensis* (ACW)⁶. Phytochemical studies have identified that *Amorphophallus commutatus* is rich in biologically active compounds including saponins and flavonoids, triterpenoids, alkaloids, and polysaccharides, which support to its wide range of pharmacological activities⁷. Previously, we reported the antibacterial, hepatoprotective, immunomodulatory anti-inflammatory and Analgesic activity of ACW. Research on the toxicity of *A. commutatus* var. *wayanadensis* methanolic extract (MEAC) validated the safety profile for usage in animals.⁶ Although *Amorphophallus commutatus* has been traditionally used for renal disorders, its diuretic activity. To the best of our knowledge, no research has been done to assess the leaves' potential for diuretic action or the types of bioactive components that contribute to it. Therefore, assessing the diuretic efficacy of the methanolic extract of *Amorphophallus*

commutatus var. *wayanadensis* (MELAC) in a rat model is the primary goal of this work

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Chemicals And Drugs

The drugs and chemical reagents utilized in the present research included distilled water, standard drug furosemide (Lasix), normal saline (0.9%), sodium chloride (NaCl), potassium chloride, potassium chromate, silver nitrate, 10% phosphate buffer formalin, chloroform, Folin–Ciocalteu reagent, gallic acid, atropine, tannic acid, absolute methanol, hydrochloric acid, Acetic acid, sulfuric acid, sodium hydroxide, sodium carbonate, and sodium nitrite, ethanol, ammonium hydroxide, DPPH, petroleum ether, chloral hydrate, phloroglucinol, glycerine, iodine, phytochemical screening reagents, rutin, and ammonium chloride. Every chemical and reagent was highly pure and of analytical quality.

2.2. Collection And Authentication Of Plant Material:

The leaves of *Amorphophallus commutatus*, was obtained at local nursery of Navi Mumbai, (Maharashtra). Mr. Mahesh Atale, M. Sc. Botany, Alarsin Pioneers in Ayurvedic Research, Andheri (E), Mumbai – 400 093, validated the plant's taxonomic identity.

2.3. Preparation Of The Methanolic Extract Of *Amorphophallus Commutatus* Leaves

After being washed, the leaves were left to dry in the shade. The dried leaves were ground with a mortar and pestle before being sieved through sieve No. 14. The powdered Before being extracted, were kept in an airtight container. By using petroleum ether (60–80°C) defatted the 100 g of dried AC leaf powder, the residue was dried and then extracted using methanol by Soxhlet until full extraction was accomplished. A revolving vacuum evaporator was used to filter the extract while it was still hot and concentrated. The dried extract samples were stored in an airtight container at a low temperature in the refrigerator for further study^{8 1 6}.

2.4 Characterisation Of *Amorphophallus Commutatus* Leaves Extract

The methanolic extract of *Amorphophallus commutatus* leaves (MELAC) was subjected to detailed macroscopic, physicochemical, organoleptic, and phytochemical evaluations to ensure extract quality and authenticity. In Organoleptic evaluation, the fresh plant was evaluated for appropriate parameters like taste, odour, size, shape and colour⁹. In order to assess the moisture content and inorganic materials, physicochemical parameters such as loss on drying, total ash, acid-insoluble ash, and water-soluble ash were calculated using standard pharmacopeial technique¹⁰.

2.5. Phytochemical Screening

Using standard methods, a qualitative phytochemical analysis of the methanolic extract was conducted to determine whether secondary metabolites such as alkaloids, amino acids, glycosides, flavonoids, cardiac glycosides, steroids, tannins, and terpenoids were present¹¹.

2.6 Total Alkaloid Content

Alkaloids are identified by applying the Harborne (1973) method. One gram of the material was weighed, 200 milliliters of 10% acetic acid in ethanol were added, the beaker was capped, and the mixture was allowed to stand for four hours. The extract was filtered and then concentrated to a fourth of its original volume in a water bath. Drop by drop, concentrated NH₄OH was added to the extract until the precipitation was complete. The precipitate was collected, washed with diluted NH₄OH, and filtered once the whole solution had had time to settle. The alkaloid is the residue that was dried and weighed¹².

2.7 Total Phenolic Content

The Folin-Ciocalteu method has been modified to determine the total phenolic content of the methanolic extract of *A. commutatus*, using gallic acid as a reference. In short, 50 µl of *Amorphophallus commutatus* methanolic extracts were mixed with 2.5 ml of Folin-Ciocalteu reagent (1:10) and allowed to sit for three minutes. After incubation, 2 milliliters of 7.5% w/v Na₂CO₃ were added, mixed well, and

allowed to stand for an hour at room temperature. Spectroscopy was then used to detect the absorbance at 765 nm. To represent the total phenolic content, gallic acid equivalent milligrams per gram of extract were utilized⁸.

2.8 Total Flavonoid Content

With a few modifications, the methanolic extract's total flavonoid content was calculated. 0.5 ml of extracts dissolved in DMSO were mixed with 3 ml of distilled water and 0.3 ml of 5% NaNO₂. After five minutes, 0.3 ml of a 10% AlCl₃ solution was added, and the mixture was incubated for two minutes. This reaction mixture's ultimate volume was 10 ml after 1M NaOH was added. The absorbance was measured using spectrophotometry at 510 nm in comparison to a reaction blank. The total flavonoid content was expressed as mg quercetin equivalent/g extract⁸.

2.9 Experimental Animals

The National Institute of Bioscience, At Dhangawadi, Tal: - Bhor, Dist.: - Pune, 412205, provided healthy adult Male Wistar rats (weighing 200–250 gm). They were housed in controlled environments with free pellet food and water, at 28 to 30°C, with a photoperiod of around 12 hours of natural light each day and a relative humidity of 50 to 55%. A veterinary surgeon from the Konkan Gyanpeeth Rahul Dharkar College of Pharmacy and Research Institute, Karjat oversaw the animal care. The Institutional Animal Ethical Committee approved the experimental protocol (approval reference no. KGRDCP/IAEC/2023-2024/15).

2.10. Evaluation Of Diuretic Activity

In all, thirty rats were employed in this study, all of which were deemed suitable for the experiments. The study was conducted in two phases, focusing on the potential acute and subacute diuretic effects of *Amorphophallus commutatus* extract. The rats were first assigned into five experimental groups, each consisting of six individuals, at random. Rats were given free access to drinking water while fasting for the whole night. To provide a consistent water load, rats were given 15 milliliters of isotonic saline (0.9% NaCl, p.o.) on the day of the experiment. Forty-five minutes later, bladders were evacuated by holding the

base of the tail and gently squeezing the pelvic area. distilled water was given to the control group. Furosemide (10 mg/kg) was administered to one standard group. Three test groups, each receiving different doses of MELAC extract (100 mg/kg, 200 mg/kg, or 400 mg/kg), administered orally using an Oral feeding needle (Oral Gavage). Rats were placed one at a time in metabolic cages for urine collection following treatment. Food and water were restricted during the 24-hour collection period. For the assessment of acute diuretic activity, urine samples were collected at 12h, and 24h intervals following the first treatment. The total urine output over 24 hours was measured, along with key indicators such as, the concentration of electrolytes (sodium, potassium, and chloride), carbonic anhydrase inhibition, and saluretic/natriuretic activities. Additionally, blood samples were drawn from the retro-orbital sinus 24 hours after the first treatment to analyse electrolyte levels, urea and creatinine. A one-day washout period was given after the 24-hour study.

To examine the subacute diuretic effects, Rats gave food, with free access to drinking water. On the everyday, rats received 15 mL of isotonic saline (0.9% NaCl, p.o.) to impose a uniform water load. After forty-five minutes, the pelvic area was gently compressed while the base of the tail was supported in order to empty the bladders. the treatment doses were administered once daily for a period of seven days in each group. Urine output, urine pH, specific gravity and electrolyte concentrations was measured after 24 hours each day^{13 14}.

2.11 Biochemical And Histological Evaluation

2.11.1 Body Weight Measurement

Every day, a digital weighing machine was used to record each animal's body weight¹³.

2.11.2 Urine Parameters Measurements

At 12 and 24 hours, the total amount of urine produced by each rat was measured. The pH of recently obtained urine samples was measured using a calibrated digital pH meter. An established formula was used to determine the urine's specific gravity, diuretic effect, and diuretic activity. A Double Beam Spectrophotometer was used to assess the quantities

of creatinine and urea in urine samples, and standard biochemical procedures were performed to evaluate the levels of Na⁺, K⁺, and Cl⁻ (flame photometry)^{15 16 17 18}.

$$\text{Specific gravity} = \frac{\text{weight of urine}}{\text{weight of water}}$$

Diuretic action

$$= \frac{\text{Urinary excretion of treatment group}}{\text{Urinary excretion of control group}}$$

Diuretic activity

$$= \frac{\text{Urinary action of test group}}{\text{Urinary action of standard group}}$$

2.11.3 Determination Of Saluretic, Natriuretic, Carbonic Anhydrase Inhibitor Activity

As a measure of saluretic activity, the amounts of Na⁺ and K⁺ were calculated. The Na⁺/K⁺ ratio was used to calculate the natriuretic activity. The inhibitory activity of carbonic anhydrase was evaluated using the Cl⁻ / (Na⁺ + K⁺) ratio^{19 20}.

2.11.4 Serum And Homogenate Parameters Measurements

Blood samples was withdrawn by retro orbital sinus method and characterised twice. Once after 24hrs i.e. on day 2 for acute study, then on day 8 of treatment for sub-acute diuretic activity from each treatment group. The levels of creatinine, urea, and electrolytes in plasma samples were measured using a Double Beam Spectrophotometer. A formula is used to determine the creatinine clearance. The glomerular filtration rate (GFR) was computed using creatinine clearance^{15 16}.

Creatinine clearance

$$= \frac{\text{Urinary excretion of treatment group}}{\text{Urinary excretion of control group}}$$

2.11.5 Determination Of Glomerular Filtration Rate

Based on serum and urine creatinine levels, glomerular filtration rate was calculated using creatinine clearance⁴.

$$\text{GFR} = \frac{\text{Urinary excretion of treatment group}}{\text{Urinary excretion of control group}}$$

2.11.6 Kidney Homogenate Preparation

Following conventional procedures, the kidneys of the treated rats were extracted and immersed in Bouin's solution for a full day in order to conduct histological analysis. Before being embedded in paraffin wax, the tissues were first dehydrated using a series of graded ethanol solutions (70%, 90%, and 100%) and then cleared using xylene. Using a Leica rotary microtome, tissue blocks were made and cut into slices that were 7 μ m thick. Poly-L-lysine was applied to the slides to guarantee good adhesion, and the tissue slices were spread out gently in a water bath maintained at 43°C. After being deparaffinized with xylene, the slides were rehydrated using a step-by-step series of ethanol concentrations for ten minutes at each level. Hematoxylin and eosin were used to stain the slides, and different alcohol concentrations were subsequently used to dehydrate them. To improve clarity, the slides were treated with xylene in the latter stages, and then they were mounted with DPX. Finally, the slides were examined and imaged using a microscope ⁴.

2.12 Statistical Analysis

In GraphPad Prism version 7.0 (GraphPad Software Inc., USA), all data are analyzed and then presented as mean \pm standard error of the mean (SEM). Both one-way and two-way analyses of variance (ANOVA) were employed for statistical comparisons, depending on the experimental design. Tukey's multiple comparison test or Dunnett's test was

employed for post hoc analysis, depending on the comparison requirements. Utilizing the corresponding p-values, statistical significance was established.

3. RESULTS:

3.1. Pharmacognostical And Phytochemical Evaluation Of *Amorphophallus Commutatus* Leaves

3.1.1. Organoleptic evaluation of *Amorphophallus commutatus* leaves

Organoleptic characteristics, including colour, odour, taste, and texture, were systematically assessed to ensure the quality and identity of the crude drug, as presented in **Error! Reference source not found.**

Table 1: Organoleptic characters of *Amorphophallus commutatus* leaves

Sr. No.	Organoleptic evaluation	Observation
1.	Colour	Brown
2.	Odour	Alismatalas
3.	Size	30- 50 cm long and 1.5 – 2m height
4.	Shape	Slightly oval to lanceolate
5.	Taste	Bitter

3.1.2 Physiochemical Characteristics:

Physicochemical parameters of *Amorphophallus commutatus* leaves were assessed to evaluate its purity and quality, as shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Physiochemical characteristics of *Amorphophallus commutatus* leaves

Sr. No.	Parameter	Results	IP limits
1.	Loss on drying	1.89% w/w	-
2.	Total ash	5.75% w/w	Not more than 10% w/w
3.	Water- soluble ash	7.24% w/w	Not more than 3% w/w
4.	Acid – insoluble ash	2.28% w/w	Not more than 6% w/w

3.1.3 Qualitative Photochemical Screening

Analyzing the methanolic extract of *Amorphophallus commutatus* leaves revealed that it included carbohydrates, alkaloids, flavonoids, glycosides, cardiac glycosides, tannins, and saponins, among other medicinally active substances. The concentrations of the flavonoids, phenolics, and total

alkaloids found in MELAC were reported to be 9.4%, 5.7%, and 17.6%, respectively.

Table 3: Preliminary phytochemical analysis of leaves extracts of *Amorphophallus commutatus*.

Test	Methanolic Extract
Carbohydrates	+
Reducing Sugars	+

Alkaloids	+
Glycosides	+
Cardiac Glycoside	+
Flavonoids	+
Triterpenoids	-
Saponins	+

Tannins	+
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3.2 Assessment Of Acute Diuretic Activity

3.2.1 Body Weight:

Table 4 shows the effects on the body weight of 24 hr treatments with the MELAC. Weight reductions were progressively more pronounced with each of the treatments. the control group exhibited a minor reduction in body weight, which may be due to handling stress or physiological variability. In

contrast, the standard group, along with all MELAC-treated groups, demonstrated a more pronounced decrease in body weight. These findings support that MELAC may exert diuretic activity, potentially by promoting the excretion of excess fluid through increased urine formation or modulation of renal function.

Table 4: Effect on body weight before and after 24-hour dosing of treatment in various groups

Groups	Body Weight (in gms \pm SEM)	
	Before dosing	After dosing
Control	239.5 \pm 5.445	234.2 \pm 5.076
Standard	245 \pm 8.359	237.2 \pm 7.795
MELAC 100mg/kg	239 \pm 6.33	233.7 \pm 5.863
MELAC 200mg/kg	239.66 \pm 6.02	234.2 \pm 5.718
MELAC 400mg/kg	238.2 \pm 4.672	235.2 \pm 4.556

Values are expressed as mean \pm SEM (n = 6) Two-way ANOVA are used.

3.2.2 Effect On Urine Output:

Table 5 specify the urine volume. Over the course of 12 and 24 hours, the total urine volume was measured for the MELAC (100, 200, and 400 mg/kg), standard (furosemide), and normal control. The findings

revealed that the effect was dosage dependant and that MELAC produced urine at all tested doses, including standard at 12 and 24 hours. MELAC and furosemide substantially higher urine flow at 12 and 24 hours compared to control rats (p <0.001).

Table 5: Urine output (mL) at 12 and 24 hours following oral administration of various treatments doses

Groups	12 Hr	24 Hr
Control	2.93 \pm 0.6004	5.86 \pm 1.362
Standard	6.5 \pm 0.595***	12.11 \pm 1.309***
MELAC 100mg/kg	2.98 \pm 0.3458	6.01 \pm 0.5618
MELAC 200mg/kg	4.33 \pm 0.7636	8.06 \pm 0.527
MELAC 400mg/kg	5.08 \pm 0.3911*	10.15 \pm 0.3538*

Values are expressed as mean \pm SEM (n = 6) Two-way ANOVA are used. ***Significant difference at P <0.001 as compared with control group.

3.2.3 Effect On Diuretic Action And Diuretic Activity:

Table 6, presents the effects of the first daily treatment with MELAC on the diuretic action and activity. Over the course of 24 hours, the diuretic action and diuretic activity were evaluated for the methanolic extracts of AC leaves (100, 200, and 400 mg/kg), standard (furosemide), and normal control. The findings

demonstrated that MELAC had diuretic impact at all tested doses, including the standard at 24 hours, and that its effects were dose dependent. When compared to control rats, furosemide and MELAC markedly increase diuretic action and diuretic activity at 24 hours.

Table 6: Comparison of diuretic action and diuretic activity of MELAC at varying doses with control and standard

S. No.	Groups	Diuretic action	Diuretic activity
1.	Control	1.00 ± 0.232	0.48 ± 0.112
2.	Standard	2.06 ± 0.223	1.00 ± 0.108***
3.	100mg/kg	1.02 ± 0.095	0.496 ± 0.046
4.	200mg/kg	1.37 ± 0.089	0.666 ± 0.043
5.	400mg/kg	1.73 ± 0.060	0.838 ± 0.029*

Diuretic action was calculated as a ratio of urine volume in treated group / urine volume in control group. Diuretic activity was calculated as a ratio of urine volume in treated group / urine volume in standard group.

Values are expressed as mean ± SEM (n = 6). ONE WAY ANOVA are used. ***Significant difference at P < 0.001 as compared with control group.

1.2.4 Impacts On The Ph And Specific Gravity Of Urine:

Table 7, shows the pH and specific gravity of urine were tested after 24 h. Urine pH in control rats was 8.17 ± 0.2448. 24 hours after 100, 200, and 400 mg/kg body weight doses of MELAC were administered, the urine pH was 7.583 ± 0.115, 7.397 ± 0.08883, and 337 ± 0.178, respectively. Furosemide made the urine significantly acidic by decreasing the pH to 6.872 ± 0.1545. The control group maintained a mean specific gravity of 1.006 ± 0.0097, indicating normal urine concentration. In contrast, the standard diuretic (furosemide) showed a reduced specific

gravity of 1.005 ± 0.0050, reflecting its known action on the renal tubules. Notably, treatment with the MELAC resulted in further reductions in urine specific gravity: 1.004 ± 0.004738 (100 mg/kg), 1.004 ± 0.004738 (200 mg/kg), and 1.002 ± 0.0139 (400 mg/kg), gives the strongest impact when taken at a dose of 400 mg/kg. (p < 0.01 vs. control and standard). These results suggest enhanced water excretion and urine dilution, indicative of a strong diuretic effect. The progressive decline in specific gravity with increasing extract dose implies a pharmacologically active component that may influence renal function.

Table 7: Effect of various treatment groups on urine pH and specific gravity after 24 hr

Groups	Urine pH	Urine Specific Gravity
Control	8.17 ± 0.2448	1.006 ± 0.009657
Standard	6.872 ± 0.1545***	1.005 ± 0.005029
100mg/kg	7.583 ± 0.115	1.004 ± 0.004738
200mg/kg	7.397 ± 0.08883*	1.003 ± 0.00458

400mg/kg	7.337 ± 0.178**	1.002 ± 0.01394
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Values are expressed as mean ± SEM (n = 6) ONE WAY ANOVA are used. Significant difference at *P < 0.01, **P < 0.001, ***P < 0.001, ****P < 0.0001, as compared with control group.

3.2.5 24 Hours After Treatment, Urine Electrolytes And Markers Of Renal Function:

Table 8 displays the saluretic and natriuretic activity, carbonic anhydrase inhibition (CAI), urine Na⁺, K⁺, and Cl⁻ levels, as well as indicators of kidney function. Beginning at 100 mg/kg and in a dose-dependent manner, the methanolic extract significantly raised urine Na⁺, K⁺, and Cl⁻ levels (P < 0.0001) in comparison to the vehicle group, which was equivalent to furosemide. Results for natriuretic,

saluretic, and carbonic anhydrase inhibition are shown in Table 6. In comparison to normal control, the MELAC at dosages of 100, 200, and 400 mg/kg and furosemide (10 mg/kg) shown strong CAI and saluretic activity. The MELAC had less of an impact on natriuretic activity in the current investigation. Additionally, kidney function markers changed as a result of the methanolic extracts. Furosemide and the MELAC raised the creatinine level considerably (P < 0.0001) in comparison to the vehicle group in a dose-dependent manner. In comparison to the vehicle group, there were notable increases in urea levels: 38.17 ± 1.012 for the extract dose of 100 mg/kg, 45.56 ± 0.921 for the 200 mg/kg dose, 50.13 ± 0.715 for the 400 mg/kg dose, and 73.11 ± 0.646 for the furosemide dose.

Table 8: 24 hours after treatment, urine electrolytes and markers of renal function:

Groups	Control	Standard (furosemide)	MELAC 100 mg/kg	MELAC 200 mg/kg	MELAC 400 mg/kg
Na⁺, Cl⁻, and K⁺ levels					
Na ⁺ (mEq/L)	23.76 ± 1.625	33.16 ± 1.078****	26.67 ± 0.6884	28.24 ± 0.5913*	31.38 ± 0.7654****
K ⁺ (mEq/L)	25.03 ± 1.265	28.19 ± 1.566	23.95 ± 0.7389	24.43 ± 0.835	26.95 ± 0.3534
Cl ⁻ (mEq/L)	16.63 ± 1.302	33.79 ± 0.9747****	25.48 ± 0.6007****	27.15 ± 0.7946****	31.08 ± 0.8671****
CAI, saluretic and natriuretic activities					
Saluretic activity	40.38 ± 2.444	66.95 ± 1.889****	52.15 ± 0.8702****	55.39 ± 0.7762****	62.45 ± 1.122****
Natriuretic activity	0.9635 ± 0.0811	1.192 ± 0.06267*	1.12 ± 0.05154	1.163 ± 0.04963	1.166 ± 0.03273
CAI	0.3417 ± 0.02373	0.5527 ± 0.0148****	0.5046 ± 0.01833****	0.5164 ± 0.01733****	0.5332 ± 0.01518****
Kidney function indicators					
Creatinine (mg/dL)	0.76 ± 0.076	1.15 ± 0.043****	0.91 ± 0.070****	0.96 ± 0.067****	1.03 ± 0.102****
Urea (mg/dL)	38.30 ± 0.992	73.11 ± 0.646	38.17 ± 1.012	45.56 ± 0.921	50.13 ± 0.715

Values are expressed as mean ± SEM (n = 6) ONE WAY ANOVA are used. Significant difference at *P < 0.01, **P < 0.001, ***P < 0.001, ****P < 0.0001, as compared with control group

3.2.6 Serum Levels Of Na⁺, K⁺, And Cl⁻ And Creatinine, Urea 24-H After Treatment:

Error! Reference source not found. presents serum Na⁺, K⁺, and Cl⁻ levels and kidney function indicators. Administration of the MELAC resulted in a dose-dependent decrease in serum sodium (Na⁺), potassium (K⁺), and chloride (Cl⁻) levels when compared to the control group. These changes were comparable to those observed in the standard group treated with a known diuretic, suggesting that the

MELAC possesses significant diuretic activity. The reduction in serum sodium indicates natriuretic activity, while the marked decrease in potassium levels points to a kaliuretic effect. Similarly, the decline in chloride levels suggests chloriuretic action. The concentration of creatinine increased significantly ($P < 0.001$) in rats that were given the extract in a dose-dependent manner. The concentration of urea decreases in rats that were given the extract in a dose-dependent manner.

Table 9: Blood levels of creatinine, urea, Na⁺, K⁺, and Cl⁻ 24-h after treatment:

Groups/ Parameters	Control	Standard (furosemide)	MELAC 100 mg/kg	MELAC 200 mg/kg	MELAC 400 mg/kg
Na ⁺ (mEq/L)	141.35 ± 0.325	131.08 ± 1.136	136.30 ± 0.666	135.03 ± 2.35	133.15 ± 1.631
K ⁺ (mEq/L)	17.45 ± 1.595	13.07 ± 0.775	11.48 ± 0.619	10.53 ± 0.550	9.812 ± 0.592
Cl ⁻ (mEq/L)	102.85 ± 1.689	88.98 ± 1.816	94.27 ± 1.108	92.56 ± 1.327	89.78 ± 0.736
Creatinine (mg/dL)	0.38 ± 0.054	0.73 ± 0.042***	0.60 ± 0.052*	0.68 ± 0.048**	0.71 ± 0.060***
Urea (mg/dL)	41.33 ± 3.180	42.72 ± 1.068**	40.83 ± 1.078*	37.55 ± 1.903**	35.87 ± 2.721***

Values are expressed as mean ± SEM (n = 6) ONE WAY ANOVA are used. Significant difference at **P < 0.001, ***P < 0.001, as compared with control group.

3.2.7 Creatinine Clearance & GFR (Glomerular Filtration Rate) Measurements:

GFR (Glomerular Filtration Rate) and creatinine clearance are displayed in Table 10. The Glomerular Filtration Rate (GFR) was calculated by calculating creatinine clearance in order to assess renal function. Table 10 compares the GFR of the standard and control groups with that of the treated animals at varying dosages. Significant changes in GFR dynamics were found in the MELAC, which showed a remarkable rise in GFR when compared to the

control group. This suggests that the extract may have a beneficial effect on renal filtration processes. Interestingly, of the groups studied, the well-known diuretic furosemide had the highest GFR value, indicating a strong effect on renal filtration. With a dosage of 400 mg/kg, MELAC was the second-highest GFR enhancer after furosemide, suggesting that it may help promote effective renal function. Together, these results highlight MELAC's possible renal advantages and support their encouraging role in promoting renal health.

Table 10: Effect of various treatment groups on Creatinine clearance & GFR (Glomerular Filtration Rate) after 24 hr.

Groups	Creatinine clearance (mg/dL)	GFR
Control	0.007 ± 0.001	3.34 ± 0.58
Standard	0.013 ± 0.001	5.80 ± 0.77
100mg/kg	0.006 ± 0.001	2.78 ± 0.41
200mg/kg	0.008 ± 0.0008	3.37 ± 0.37
400mg/kg	0.010 ± 0.001	4.40 ± 0.60

Values are expressed as mean ± SEM (n = 6). ONE WAY ANOVA are used.

3.3. Assessment Of Sub - Acute Diuretic Activity

3.3.1 Body Weight:

Table 11 presents the effects of one week of treatment with MELAC on the body weight. Everyday treatment resulted in progressively more noticeable drops in body weight. the control group exhibited a minor reduction in body weight, which may be due to handling stress or physiological variability. In contrast, the standard group, along with all MELAC-

treated groups, demonstrated a more pronounced decrease in body weight over 7 days. These findings support that MELAC may exert diuretic activity, potentially by promoting the excretion of excess fluid through increased urine formation or modulation of renal function.

Table 11: Body Weight changes after seven days of daily treatment

Sr. No	Days/Groups	Control	Std	100	200	400
1	DAY 1	234.2 ± 5.076*	237.2 ± 7.795	232.2 ± 5.665	233.3 ± 5.608	231.7 ± 3.739
2	DAY 2	232.8 ± 4.847	234.5 ± 7.886	230.3 ± 5.321	231.2 ± 5.486	229.7 ± 3.739
3	DAY 3	230.8 ± 4.75	230.2 ± 8.002	229.5 ± 5.755	228.8 ± 5.029	227.3 ± 3.712
4	DAY 4	228.5 ± 4.537	227.2 ± 7.296	228.3 ± 5.613	226.3 ± 5.004	225 ± 3.55
5	DAY 5	225.7 ± 4.462	226.5 ± 7.71	227.8 ± 4.658	224.8 ± 4.757	223 ± 3.194
6	DAY 6	222.3 ± 4.485	222.3 ± 7.856	225.8 ± 2.626	223.3 ± 3.989	220.5 ± 2.705
7	DAY 7	221.2 ± 4.686	218.7 ± 7.779	224.5 ± 2.125	222.8 ± 3.516	219.5 ± 2.446
Mean		227.92	228.08	228.34	227.21	225.24

Values are expressed as mean ± SEM (n = 6). ONE WAY ANOVA are used.

3.3.2 Effect On Urine Output:

All experimental groups' cumulative urine volume over a seven-day period was calculated. Table 12 contains comprehensive information about urine volume. When compared to the control group, the (MELAC) revealed a rise in urine output that was dose-dependent. Interestingly, MELAC at 400 mg/kg

showed the greatest diuresis, whereas MELAC at the same dosage demonstrated peak activity over 7 days. When furosemide was administered, there was an increase in urine volume in comparison to the control. Furthermore, MELAC significantly increased urine output compared to the control group, even at the lowest dosage of 100 mg/kg.

Table 12: Cumulated urine volume (ml) over 7 days of daily treatments

Sr. No	Days/Groups	Control	Std	100	200	400
1	DAY 1	5.767 ± 1.148	12.37 ± 0.5772****	7.033 ± 0.2362	8.467 ± 0.2362*	10.05 ± 0.2094***
2	DAY 2	6.167 ± 0.3774	13.73 ± 1.473****	8.083 ± 0.3919	9.95 ± 0.2566**	11.32 ± 0.325***
3	DAY 3	7.667 ± 0.5097	15.43 ± 0.9848****	11.47 ± 0.5364***	12.82 ± 0.2587****	13.13 ± 0.182****
4	DAY 4	7.217 ± 0.8784	17.57 ± 0.9376****	12.95 ± 0.2849****	13.77 ± 0.2305****	15.03 ± 0.1647****
5	DAY 5	7.767 ± 0.2092	23 ± 1.211****	19.07 ± 0.3499****	20.62 ± 0.5431****	21.32 ± 0.8731****
6	DAY 6	7.4 ± 0.3435	25.5 ± 2.141****	22.95 ± 0.3063****	23.47 ± 0.1867****	23.61 ± 0.628****

Sr. No	Days/Groups	Control	Std	100	200	400
7	DAY 7	7.75 ± 0.7924	28.2 ± 1.414****	24.67 ± 0.8709****	25.8 ± 0.6678****	26.46 ± 0.5628****
Mean		7.105	19.4	15.17	16.41	17.27

Values are expressed as mean ± SEM (n = 6) ONE WAY ANOVA are used. Significant difference at *P < 0.01, **P < 0.001, ***P < 0.001, ****P < 0.0001, as compared with control group.

3.3.3 Diuretic Action:

Table 13 present the effects of 7 days of treatment with MELAC on the diuretic action. The administration of the MELAC demonstrated a

significant and dose-dependent diuretic action over the 7-day evaluation period, compared to the control group. all treated groups exhibited a progressive increase in diuretic action, with the 400 mg/kg dose producing the highest diuretic response.

Table 13: Comparison of diuretic action at various treatment groups over 7 days

Sr. No	Days/Groups	Control	Std	100	200	400
1	DAY 1	1.00 ± 0.199	2.14 ± 0.100****	1.22 ± 0.041	1.47 ± 0.055*	1.74 ± 0.036****
2	DAY 2	1.00 ± 0.061	2.22 ± 0.239****	1.31 ± 0.064	1.61 ± 0.042***	1.83 ± 0.053****
3	DAY 3	1.00 ± 0.067	2.01 ± 0.129****	1.49 ± 0.070**	1.67 ± 0.034***	1.71 ± 0.024****
4	DAY 4	1.00 ± 0.122	2.43 ± 0.130****	1.79 ± 0.040****	1.90 ± 0.032****	2.08 ± 0.023****
5	DAY 5	1.00 ± 0.156	3.44 ± 0.289****	2.45 ± 0.045****	2.65 ± 0.070****	2.74 ± 0.113****
6	DAY 6	1.00 ± 0.046	3.44 ± 0.289****	3.10 ± 0.041****	3.17 ± 0.025****	3.19 ± 0.085****
7	DAY 7	1.00 ± 0.102	3.63 ± 0.182****	3.18 ± 0.112****	3.32 ± 0.086****	3.41 ± 0.073****
Mean		1	2.758571429	2.077142857	2.255714286	2.385714286

Values are expressed as mean ± SEM (n = 6) ONE WAY ANOVA are used. Significant difference at *P < 0.01, **P < 0.001, ***P < 0.001, ****P < 0.0001, as compared with control group.

3.3.4 Diuretic Activity

Table 14 shows the diuretic activity after seven days of MELAC treatment and compares it to the control and standard drug. The results showed that MELAC

had dose-dependent diuretic effect at all tested dosages, including standard throughout a 7-day period. Over the course of a seven-day treatment, furosemide and MELAC significantly increased diuretic activity in comparison to control rats.

Table 14: Comparison of diuretic activity at various treatment groups over 7 days

SR.NO	DAYS/ GROUPS	CONTROL	STD	100	200	400
1	DAY 1	0.46 ± 0.093	0.46 ± 0.047****	0.46 ± 0.019	0.46 ± 0.025***	0.46 ± 0.017****
2	DAY 2	0.44 ± 0.027	1.00 ± 0.107****	0.58 ± 0.029	0.72 ± 0.019****	0.82 ± 0.024****

SR.NO	DAYS/ GROUPS	CONTROL	STD	100	200	400
3	DAY 3	0.49 ± 0.033	1.00 ± 0.064****	0.74 ± 0.035***	0.83 ± 0.017****	0.85 ± 0.012****
4	DAY 4	0.41 ± 0.050	1.00 ± 0.053****	0.73 ± 0.016****	0.78 ± 0.013****	0.85 ± 0.009****
5	DAY 5	0.33 ± 0.009	1.00 ± 0.053****	0.82 ± 0.015****	0.89 ± 0.024****	0.92 ± 0.038****
6	DAY 6	0.29 ± 0.013	1.00 ± 0.084****	0.90 ± 0.012****	0.92 ± 0.007****	0.92 ± 0.025****
7	DAY 7	0.27 ± 0.028	1.00 ± 0.050****	0.87 ± 0.031****	0.91 ± 0.024****	0.93 ± 0.020****
Mean		0.384	0.922	0.728	0.787	0.821

Values are expressed as mean ± SEM (n = 6) ONE WAY ANOVA are used. Significant difference at *P < 0.01, **P < 0.001, ***P < 0.001, ****P < 0.0001, as compared with control group.

3.3.5 Estimation Of Urine Ph:

MELAC affected urine pH revealed that treated rats pH levels differed significantly from controls, as shown in Table 15. The urinary pH of the control rats consistently exhibited an alkaline urinary pH throughout the experimental period (ranging from 8.01 to 8.36), indicating normal renal function without any acidifying stimulus. The rats treated with furosemide at a dose of 10 mg/kg exhibited a significant and sustained reduction in urinary pH

shows acidification of urine. When compared to the control, the rats given varying dosages of MELAC had a dose-dependent decrease in urine pH. The most noticeable acidifying effect was caused by the highest dose (400 mg/kg), and by Day 7, the values were comparable to those of the standard group. The progressive acidification of urine in the treated groups suggests that the extract may enhance the excretion of acidic metabolites or inhibit bicarbonate reabsorption, reflecting a diuretic-like action.

Table 15: Effect of various treatment groups on urine pH over 7 days

Sr. No	Days/ Groups	Control	Std	100	200	400
1	DAY 1	8.36 ± 0.343	7.61 ± 0.329	7.42 ± 0.238	7.24 ± 0.192	6.88 ± 0.206
2	DAY 2	8.06 ± 0.158	7.50 ± 0.229	7.06 ± 0.245	7.20 ± 0.111	7.02 ± 0.246
3	DAY 3	8.01 ± 0.472	6.66 ± 0.203	6.971 ± 0.161	6.80 ± 0.200	6.95 ± 0.115
4	DAY 4	8.24 ± 0.474	6.24 ± 0.178	6.77 ± 0.225	6.86 ± 0.175	6.905 ± 0.140
5	DAY 5	8.045 ± 0.309	6.95 ± 0.249	6.79 ± 0.162	6.875 ± 0.187	6.71 ± 0.142
6	DAY 6	8.13 ± 0.315	6.72 ± 0.231	6.825 ± 0.260	6.93 ± 0.221	6.79 ± 0.153
7	DAY 7	8.19 ± 0.321	6.79 ± 0.242	6.77 ± 0.148	6.91 ± 0.216	6.97 ± 0.123
Mean		8.14	6.92	6.94	6.97	6.88

Values are expressed as mean ± SEM (n = 6) TWO WAY ANOVA are used

3.3.6 Estimation Of Urine Specific Gravity:

The analysis of urinary specific gravity (SG) over the seven-day treatment period with the MELAC show in Table 16, revealed a consistent trend indicative of specific gravity. On Day 1, a markedly elevated SG value (1.14) was observed in Control, potentially attributable to transient dehydration or inter-

individual physiological variation. The remaining groups on Day 1 exhibited SG values within the physiological range (1.01–1.02), which served as the baseline for subsequent comparisons. From Day 2 onwards, the SG values demonstrated a sustained reduction and stabilization within a narrow interval (1.00–1.02) across all groups, suggesting a progressive dilution of urinary solutes. Overall, the

observed SG profile provides compelling evidence corroborating its potential utility in modulating fluid that the MELAC exerts a diuretic effect, balance.

Table 16: Effect of various treatment groups on urine specific gravity over 7 days

SR.NO	DAYS/ GROUPS	CONTROL	STD	100	200	400
1	DAY 1	1.14 ± 0.108	1.02 ± 0.004****	1.01 ± 0.004****	1.01 ± 0.009****	1.02 ± 0.004****
2	DAY 2	1.00 ± 0.012	1.01 ± 0.005	1.01 ± 0.004	1.01 ± 0.004	1.01 ± 0.004
3	DAY 3	1.00 ± 0.003	1.01 ± 0.003	1.01 ± 0.003	1.02 ± 0.002	1.02 ± 0.002
4	DAY 4	1.02 ± 0.004	1.02 ± 0.002	1.02 ± 0.001	1.01 ± 0.005	1.01 ± 0.003
5	DAY 5	1.02 ± 0.001	1.02 ± 0.002	1.02 ± 0.002	1.01 ± 0.004	1.01 ± 0.003
6	DAY 6	1.02 ± 0.002	1.02 ± 0.001	1.02 ± 0.001	1.01 ± 0.002	1.01 ± 0.001
7	DAY 7	1.02 ± 0.001	1.02 ± 0.001	1.01 ± 0.001	1.01 ± 0.002	1.006 ± 0.001
Mean		1.03	1.01	1.01	1.01	1.01

Values are expressed as mean ± SEM (n = 6). ****Significant difference at P < 0.0001 as compared with control group.

3.3.7 Estimation Of Urine Electrolytes:

The urinary electrolyte content of 7 days of daily treatments shows in Tables 17–19. The control group had the lowest urine electrolyte level, whereas furosemide once again had the highest. With its electrolyte excretion efficacy, the MELAC exhibited

relatively mild diuretic responses at all dosages in contrast to rats used as normal controls. During the seven days of treatment, the MELAC at doses of 100 mg/kg, 200 mg/kg, and 400 mg/kg markedly and dose-dependently enhanced the excretion of Na⁺, K⁺, and Cl⁻.

Na⁺ Excretion:

Table 17: Na⁺ Excretion (mEq/L) in Different Treatment Groups Across 7 Days

SR.NO	DAYS/ GROUPS	CONTROL	STD	100	200	400
1	DAY 1	23.69 ± 1.117	34.19 ± 1.1***	25.63 ± 0.9467*	31.3±1.507**	32.18±0.5346**
2	DAY 2	23.46 ± 1.388	37.04 ± 1.464****	34.35 ± 1.28****	35.61±1.947*** *	36.32±1.454*** *
3	DAY 3	24.96 ± 1.29	41.3 ± 1.875****	37.77 ± 0.5374****	38.11±0.7827** **	39.51±0.8223** **
4	DAY 4	24.15 ± 0.9261	47.74 ± 1.834****	42.7±0.6495*** *	44.68±0.5646** **	46.42±0.4255** **
5	DAY 5	24.33 ± 1.614	54.2 ± 1.95****	42.77±1.267*** *	45.94±0.8338** **	51.31±0.4702** **
6	DAY 6	24.98 ± 1.659	57.05 ± 1.897****	48.88±1.397*** *	50.04±1.099*** *	54.25±0.5319** **
7	DAY 7	26.73 ± 1.117	60.28 ± 1.1****	54 ± 0.946****	55.26 ± 1.507****	57.42 ± 0.534****
Mean		24.61	47.4	40.87	42.99	45.34

Values are expressed as mean ± SEM (n = 6) ONE WAY ANOVA are used. Significant difference at *P < 0.01, **P < 0.001, ***P < 0.001, ****P < 0.0001, as compared with control group.

K⁺ Excretion:**Table 18: K⁺ Excretion (mEq/L) in Different Treatment Groups Across 7 Days**

SR.NO	DAYS / GROUPS	CONTROL	STD	100	200	400
1	DAY 1	21.77 ± 0.9854	28.31 ± 1.439***	22.07 ± 0.6688	23.37 ± 0.8447	25.73 ± 0.5913*
2	DAY 2	28.64 ± 1.699	28.64 ± 2.213	28.64 ± 0.6939	28.64 ± 1.615	28.64 ± 1.223
3	DAY 3	24.32 ± 1.115	31.69 ± 1.576	25.49 ± 0.7423	26.77 ± 0.6778	29.79 ± 0.6924
4	DAY 4	25.8 ± 1.125	33.3 ± 3.131	27.47 ± 0.5382	29.85 ± 0.8243	31.81 ± 1.253
5	DAY 5	24.86 ± 0.8297	38.86 ± 1.518****	33.06 ± 0.9362****	34.74 ± 0.4286****	36.71 ± 0.8296****
6	DAY 6	27.09 ± 0.7305	41.05 ± 1.421****	36.33 ± 0.5935****	38.23 ± 0.7906****	39.98 ± 0.9472****
7	DAY 7	24.41 ± 0.9854	43.75 ± 1.439****	37.69 ± 0.6688****	39.4 ± 0.8447****	41.45 ± 0.5913****
Mean		25.27	35.08	30.10	31.57	33.44

Values are expressed as mean ± SEM (n = 6) ONE WAY ANOVA are used. Significant difference at *P < 0.01, **P < 0.001, ***P < 0.001, ****P < 0.0001, as compared with control group.

Cl⁻ Excretion:**Table 19: Cl⁻ Excretion (mEq/L) in Different Treatment Groups Across 7 Days**

SR.NO	DAYS / GROUPS	CONTROL	STD	100	200	400
1	DAY 1	23.94 ± 1.044	30.57 ± 1.73**	25.86 ± 1.168	27.55 ± 0.5907	28.14 ± 0.6822*
2	DAY 2	25.48 ± 1.229	32.27 ± 1.332***	27.18 ± 0.8496	28.11 ± 0.9628	30.94 ± 1.211**
3	DAY 3	25.21 ± 1.106	33.12 ± 1.709***	27.69 ± 0.8499	29.21 ± 1.164	31.34 ± 0.7865**
4	DAY 4	25.37 ± 0.8144	35.85 ± 2.173****	29.35 ± 0.5816	31.98 ± 1.011**	33.76 ± 0.8118***
5	DAY 5	26.57 ± 1.525	39.86 ± 2.292****	32.32 ± 2.292*	35.3 ± 0.8982***	37.07 ± 0.7787****
6	DAY 6	25.25 ± 1.402	42.38 ± 2.031****	37.71 ± 0.925****	38.22 ± 1.275****	40.6 ± 0.842****
7	DAY 7	23.63 ± 0.8205	46.91 ± 1.547****	41.55 ± 0.8122****	42.96 ± 0.7348****	44.47 ± 1.293****
Mean		25.06	37.28	31.66	33.33	35.18

Values are expressed as mean ± SEM (n = 6) ONE WAY ANOVA are used. Significant difference at *P < 0.01, **P < 0.001, ***P < 0.001, ****P < 0.0001, as compared with control group.

3.3.8 Estimations Of Saluretic, Natriuretic And Carbonic Anhydrase Activity:

Saliuretic, natriuretic, and carbonic anhydrase inhibition data during a 7-day period are shown in

Tables 20–22. When compared to normal control, the furosemide (10 mg/kg) and MELAC at dosages of 100, 200, and 400 mg/kg shown strong saliuretic natriuretic and CAI action.

Saluretic Activity:

Table 20: Quantitative analysis of Saluretic activity of various treatment groups over 7 days

SR.NO	DAYS / GROUPS	CONTROL	STD	100	200	400
1	DAY 1	47.62 ± 2.002	64.75 ± 2.292****	51.49 ± 1.671	58.84 ± 1.928****	60.32 ± 1.359****
2	DAY 2	48.938 ± 1.735	69.308 ± 2.197****	61.528 ± 1.118****	63.723 ± 1.620****	67.262 ± 1.062****
3	DAY 3	50.162 ± 1.920	74.423 ± 2.892****	65.455 ± 1.192****	67.320 ± 0.988****	70.850 ± 0.605****
4	DAY 4	49.522 ± 0.795	83.595 ± 3.107****	72.048 ± 0.340****	76.662 ± 1.430****	80.178 ± 0.722****
5	DAY 5	50.897 ± 1.620	94.063 ± 3.364****	75.083 ± 1.685****	81.247 ± 0.794****	88.377 ± 1.081****
6	DAY 6	50.227 ± 1.877	99.427 ± 3.222****	86.593 ± 1.550****	88.260 ± 1.659****	94.857 ± 1.129****
7	DAY 7	50.357 ± 1.695	107.188 ± 1.870****	95.543 ± 1.673****	98.223 ± 1.791****	101.890 ± 1.426****
Mean		49.67	84.67	72.53	76.32	80.53

Values are expressed as mean ± SEM (n = 6) ONE WAY ANOVA are used. Significant difference at *P < 0.01, **P < 0.001, ***P < 0.001, ****P < 0.0001, as compared with control group.

Natriuretic activity:

Table 21: Quantitative analysis of Natriuretic activity of various treatment groups over 7 days

SR.NO	DAYS / GROUPS	CONTROL	STD	100	200	400
1	DAY 1	1.09 ± 0.059	1.21 ± 0.047	1.11 ± 0.086	1.17 ± 0.08*	1.18 ± 0.053
2	DAY 2	1.07 ± 0.077	1.24 ± 0.081	1.19 ± 0.066**	1.21 ± 0.086**	1.22 ± 0.043
3	DAY 3	1.03 ± 0.076	1.31 ± 0.078**	1.26 ± 0.050****	1.27 ± 0.052****	1.29 ± 0.052**
4	DAY 4	0.95 ± 0.070	1.56 ± 0.171****	1.46 ± 0.032****	1.49 ± 0.046****	1.52 ± 0.052****
5	DAY 5	0.97 ± 0.059	1.40 ± 0.064****	1.29 ± 0.057**	1.32 ± 0.030***	1.38 ± 0.032****
6	DAY 6	0.92 ± 0.080	1.39 ± 0.038****	1.31 ± 0.048****	1.34 ± 0.036***	1.36 ± 0.032****
7	DAY 7	1.09 ± 0.033	1.38 ± 0.040**	1.33 ± 0.042***	1.35 ± 0.052**	1.36 ± 0.026**
Mean		1.01	1.35	1.27	1.30	1.33

Values are expressed as mean ± SEM (n = 6) ONE WAY ANOVA are used. Significant difference at *P < 0.01, **P < 0.001, ***P < 0.001, ****P < 0.0001, as compared with control group.

Carbonic Anhydrase Inhibition (CAI):

Table 22: Quantitative analysis of carbonic anhydrase inhibition (CAI) of various treatment groups over 7 days

SR.NO	DAYS / GROUPS	CONTROL	STD	100	200	400
1	DAY 1	0.529 ± 0.021	0.496 ± 0.041	0.42 ± 0.026	0.45 ± 0.023	0.47 ± 0.022
2	DAY 2	0.560 ± 0.029	0.483 ± 0.029	0.41 ± 0.017**	0.43 ± 0.022**	0.46 ± 0.026*
3	DAY 3	0.515 ± 0.028	0.456 ± 0.025	0.39 ± 0.012	0.41 ± 0.021	0.42 ± 0.014

SR.NO	DAYS / GROUPS	CONTROL	STD	100	200	400
4	DAY 4	0.510 ± 0.023	0.449 ± 0.037	0.419 ± 0.013*	0.429 ± 0.015*	0.432 ± 0.013
5	DAY 5	0.547 ± 0.043	0.430 ± 0.028**	0.40 ± 0.020***	0.40 ± 0.014**	0.41 ± 0.010***
6	DAY 6	0.487 ± 0.031	0.433 ± 0.021	0.39 ± 0.015	0.41 ± 0.019	0.42 ± 0.011
7	DAY 7	0.479 ± 0.012	0.451 ± 0.014	0.41 ± 0.008	0.41 ± 0.008	0.43 ± 0.013
Mean		0.518	0.456	0.405571429	0.419857143	0.434571429

Values are expressed as mean ± SEM (n = 6) ONE WAY ANOVA are used. Significant difference at *P < 0.01, **P < 0.001, ***P < 0.001, ****P < 0.0001, as compared with control group.

3.3.9 Serum Levels Of Electrolytes After 7 Days Of Treatment:

Serum levels of Na⁺, K⁺, and Cl⁻ are shown in Table 23. When compared to the control group, the MELAC administration caused a dose-dependent drop in blood levels of sodium (Na⁺), potassium (K⁺), and chloride (Cl⁻). These changes were comparable to those

observed in the standard group treated with a known diuretic, suggesting that the methanolic extract possesses significant diuretic activity. The reduction in serum sodium indicates natriuretic activity, while the marked decrease in potassium levels points to a kaliuretic effect. Similarly, the decline in chloride levels suggests chloriuretic action.

Table 23: Serum levels of electrolytes after 7 days of treatment

Groups/ Parameters	Control	Standard(furosemide)	MELAC 100 mg/kg	MELAC 200 mg/kg	MELAC 400 mg/kg
Na ⁺ (mEq/L)	143.16 ± 0.677	123.76 ± 1.663	146.58 ± 1.059	144.31 ± 1.712	132.78 ± 1.250
K ⁺ (mEq/L)	19.90 ± 0.650	15.19 ± 0.795	14.74 ± 0.233	13.44 ± 0.761	12.62 ± 0.403
Cl ⁻ (mEq/L)	102.80 ± 1.043	99.61 ± 0.555	99.90 ± 0.408	98.83 ± 0.70	96.12 ± 0.455
Creatinine (mg/dL)	0.46 ± 0.033	0.75 ± 0.067	0.56 ± 0.067	0.68 ± 0.060	0.71 ± 0.060

3.3.10 Urinary And Serum Urea Levels On Day 8 After MELAC Administration

Table 24 Show the urinary and Serum Urea Levels on Day 8 After MELAC, significantly enhanced urinary urea excretion and decrease serum urea levels in a

dose-dependent way. By Day 8, the 400 mg/kg dose closely matched the effects of furosemide.

Table 24: Effect of various treatment groups on urine and serum urea levels after 7 days

Groups	Urine Urea (mg/dL)	Serum Urea (mg/dL)
Control	38.13 ± 0.656	52.61 ± 1.909
Standard	79.31 ± 0.601	50.04 ± 1.839
100mg/kg	47.18 ± 1.240	41.26 ± 0.542
200mh/kg	49.0 ± 0.747	37.82 ± 1.016
400mg/kg	50.97 ± 1.018	30.76 ± 0.384

Values are expressed as mean ± SEM (n = 6) TWO WAY ANOVA are used.

3.3.11 Urinary And Serum Creatinine Levels On Day 8 After MELAC Administration

Table 25 Show the urinary and Serum creatinine Levels on Day 8 After MELAC of treatment, On Day 8, MELAC significantly elevated urinary creatinine and reduced serum creatinine levels in a dose-

dependent manner compared to control, indicating improved renal clearance. The 400 mg/kg group showed urinary creatinine (0.96 ± 0.061 mg/dL) and serum creatinine (0.71 ± 0.060 mg/dL), closely matching the standard furosemide group.

Table 25: Effect of various treatment groups on urine and serum Creatinine levels after 7 days

Groups	Urine Creatinine (mg/dL)	Serum Creatinine (mg/dL)
Control	0.75 ± 0.062	0.46 ± 0.033
Standard	1.63 ± 0.092	0.75 ± 0.067
100mg/kg	0.80 ± 0.045	0.56 ± 0.067
200mg/kg	0.91 ± 0.048	0.68 ± 0.060
400mg/kg	0.96 ± 0.061	0.71 ± 0.060

Values are expressed as mean \pm SEM (n = 6) TWO WAY ANOVA are used.

3.3.12 Creatinine Clearance & GFR (Glomerular Filtration Rate) On Day 8 After MELAC Administration:

GFR (Glomerular filtration rate) and creatinine clearance are displayed in Table 26. Creatinine clearance was calculated in order to quantify the Glomerular Filtration Rate (GFR), which is a measure of renal function. The GFR of the treated rats at different doses is contrasted with that of the standard and control groups in Table 26. Significant alterations in GFR dynamics were seen in the methanolic extract,

with an increase in GFR relative to the control group, suggesting a potential positive impact on renal filtration processes. The well-known diuretic furosemide, which has a significant impact on renal filtration, was interestingly found to have the highest GFR value among the groups under study. At 400 mg/kg, MELAC was the second-highest GFR enhancer after furosemide, indicating that it could help sustain renal function. All of these results highlight MELAC's possible advantages for the kidneys, confirming its encouraging function in promoting renal health.

Table 26: Effect of various treatment groups on Creatinine clearance & GFR (Glomerular Filtration Rate) after 7 days treatment

Groups	Creatinine clearance	GFR
Control	0.011 ± 0.001	5.26 ± 0.64
Standard	0.043 ± 0.004	20.04 ± 1.68
100mg/kg	0.026 ± 0.003	11.73 ± 1.81
200mg/kg	0.025 ± 0.002	11.36 ± 1.32
400mg/kg	0.026 ± 0.003	11.92 ± 1.64

Values are expressed as mean \pm SEM (n = 6) TWO WAY ANOVA are used.

3.3.13 Histopathological Evaluation

Figure 1: Control Group

Figure 2: STD Group

Figure 3: MELAC 100mg/kg

Figure 4: MELAC 200mg/kg

Figure 5: MELAC 400MG/Kg

Histological evaluation of renal tissues across all experimental groups demonstrated preserved kidney morphology. No structural alterations, inflammatory infiltration, interstitial fibrosis, or tubular vacuolization were evident in the glomeruli, tubules, or interstitium, even at the highest MELAC dose (400 mg/kg). These findings suggest that both MELAC and furosemide, at tested doses, did not induce nephrotoxic effects. Although mild tubular

epithelial hypertrophy might occur due to increased ion transport activity, such changes were not prominently observed in this study, as shown in figure 1,2,3,4 and 5.

DISCUSSION

Growing public interest and acceptability in both developed and developing nations has led to a steady increase in the use of medicinal plants and phytonutrients, including nutraceuticals. Natural

plant-based products, especially medicinal herbs, are becoming more well-known for their effectiveness in treating renal disease and related conditions. The low efficacy of contemporary medicines in treating chronic diseases is frequently cited as the reason for this growing interest in traditional medicine.

Amorphophallus commutatus is one such plant known for its nutritional and therapeutic properties. Traditionally, its leaves have been employed in the treatment of urinary disorders, particularly as a remedy for hemorrhoids and as a diuretic. The current study evaluated the diuretic potential of a methanolic extract of *Amorphophallus commutatus* leaves (MELAC). The findings demonstrated a dose-dependent enhancement in urinary output, along with accelerated fluid elimination and a moderate increase in the excretion of sodium (Na^+), potassium (K^+), and chloride (Cl^-) ions in both acute and sub-acute models. Interestingly, the diuretic effects of the 400 mg/kg dosage of MELAC were similar to those of the standard drug furosemide. An increase in saluretic, natriuretic, and carbonic anhydrase inhibitory (CAI) activity following MELAC treatment may partly account for the observed diuretic response. These effects are probably influenced by the presence of bioactive phytochemicals such as flavonoids, saponins, tannins, and phenolic compounds. Additionally, it appears that MELAC is safe at the studied dosages because there were no appreciable changes in body weight or blood creatinine levels.

Overall, these findings give scientific support for the traditional use of *Amorphophallus commutatus* in the management of renal and fluid retention disorders.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this study offers scientific support for the traditional use of *Amorphophallus commutatus* leaves as a natural diuretic. The methanolic extract (MELAC) exhibited significant, dose-dependent diuretic activity, with the 400 mg/kg dose showing effects comparable to those of the standard diuretic, furosemide. MELAC preserved normal renal function without showing any symptoms of toxicity while efficiently increasing urine volume and improving the excretion of sodium, potassium, and chloride ions. These outcomes suggest its potential role in renal protection and therapeutic management of fluid

retention conditions, including hypertension and renal disorders. Further research is necessary to isolate the bioactive constituents, clarify the underlying mechanisms of action, and assess long-term safety through clinical evaluation.

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